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Precision Performance Engineering: Aviation Chassis Development

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Technical note

Keywords:

Aerodynamics, CFD, lift-to-drag ratio, subsonic flow, SimScale, Cessna 177, Airbus A320

Abstract

This study focuses on the difference in efficiency and flow characteristics for various aircraft types through the subsonic flight regime. Three representative aircraft types were chosen: a glider, a Cessna 177, and an Airbus A320-200, to compare aerodynamic behavior across different flight categories and design concepts. The goal of the study is to analyse how lift and drag coefficients, aspect ratio, and wing geometry influence operational efficiency. The research methodology combines Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations using the SimScale platform for the general aviation models with validated manufacturer performance data for the airliner to overcome meshing limitations. The results demonstrate a clear aerodynamic progression through different models. The Cessna 177 achieved a lift-to-drag ratio of approximately 6, consistent with stability-focused design, while the Airbus A320 achieved a ratio of roughly 18, representing optimized transonic efficiency. The data confirms the direct relation between drag reduction, economic fuel saving, and environmental sustainability. [1]

1. Introduction

The aviation industry is continuously driven by the necessity to optimize safety, operational efficiency, and environmental performance. The primary contributor to an aircraft's performance profile is its aerodynamic characteristic, specifically the generation of lift relative to resultant drag. In subsonic flight conditions, where the majority of commercial and general aviation operates, maximizing the Lift-to-Drag (L/D) ratio is the critical engineering challenge. An optimized aerodynamic design directly correlates to reduced thrust requirements, that lower fuel consumption and mitigate CO₂ emissions. [1]

In the past, aerodynamic performance has been evaluated through physical wind tunnel testing and analytical calculations. While wind tunnel testing provides high-fidelity data regarding boundary layer

transition and interference drag, it requires large extent of computational resources and is often inaccessible for preliminary academic research. Conversely, analytical methods, such as Prandtl's lifting-line theory, use simplified equations to estimate induced drag (C_{Di}) based on aspect ratio and span efficiency. However, these mathematical models regularly assume ideal potential flow and fail to capture complex viscous phenomena, for example, flow separation and pressure drag on non-elliptical planforms.[2] [3] [4]

The solution implemented in this study utilises Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) via the SimScale Platform. This approach numerically solves the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations.[5] This study specially employs the $k-\omega$ SST (Shear Stress Transport) turbulence model. This model was selected for its superior ability to resolve flow behavior in the near-wall viscous sublayer while switching to standard behaviour in the free stream, making it highly effective for predicting flow separation on wing surfaces.[6] [7]

The purpose of the thesis is to conduct a comparative aerodynamic analysis of three distinct aircraft categories: a general-purpose glider, a General Aviation aircraft (Cessna 177), and a commercial airliner (Airbus A320-200). By the help of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), the study aims to quantify dimensionless parameters in order to understand how geometric factors, such as Aspect Ratio (AR), wing sweep, and surface area, influence performance. Furthermore, the research evaluates the applicability of cloud-based numerical simulation tools (SimScale) for academic analysis, identifying their capabilities in visualizing pressure distribution and their technical limitations when applied to complex transport-category airframes.[1] [11]

2. Research infrastructure: Computational Fluid Dynamics Environment

The primary objective of this study relies on computational methodologies rather than physical wind tunnel testing to simulate complex flow phenomena. The core investigation utilises Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) carried out on the SimScale cloud platform. All measurements were performed using the simulation platform tools that utilise the finite-volume method (FVM) to solve the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations. [5] This ensures realistic modelling of the turbulent airflows at different Reynolds numbers and allows the assessment of aerodynamic performance over different aircraft categories. For the steady-state RANS simulations, the $k-\omega$ SST (Shear Stress Transport) turbulence model was chosen because of its reliability in external aerodynamics and near-wall accuracy. [6] [7] Prior to simulation, geometric preprocessing, scaling, and cleanup were conducted using the FreeCAD open-source environment. [1]

The project was carried out at the Vehicle Research Center. The Industry 5.0-Based Cyber-Physical Intelligent Robotics & UAV-Avionics Laboratory [23] houses a wide range of industrial equipment [19], which enables the construction and testing of systems in a real-world environment [20]. Conclusions can then be drawn from the results of the individual measurements [18] [21]. Developments related to Artificial Intelligence [15] are also taking place here in the fields of industrial robotics [16] and drones [17], as well as in the AGV-AMR sector [22].

Figure 1. Industry 5.0 Based Cyber-Physical Intelligent Robotics & UAV-Avionics Laboratory in Vehicle Research Center

3. Technical Workflow: CFD Simulation and Analysis

3.1 Model Selection and Geometric Pre-processing

Three characteristic aircraft were chosen for the comparative study. Each model represents a different fixed-wing aircraft category. These geometries are the A320-200 (airliner), Cessna 177 Cardinal (general aviation aircraft), and Glider. The aircraft cover the design range from low-speed, high-aspect-ratio sailplanes to medium-speed, moderate-AR aeroplanes and high-speed, swept-wing transport aircraft.[1]

Figure 2: A320-200 CFD model sideview

Figure 3: Cessna 177 CFD model sideview

The preprocessing roadmap includes the geometric cleanup, simplification, sealing (watertight), and extraction of geometric reference data. Starting in FreeCAD, interior parts and non-aerodynamic details were hidden and deleted. Independent elements were merged using the Boolean fuse to combine separate wing and fuselage panels. Finally, the models were imported to SimScale and mathematically scaled to match real-world dimensions, ensuring that the Reynolds numbers calculated during simulation were similar to actual flight operations. [1]

3.2 Physics Setup and Atmospheric Calculations

To maximise the accuracy of the simulation, the necessary parameters had to be calculated for air at the chosen altitudes using International Standard Atmosphere troposphere relations. [8] The dynamic viscosity was produced via Sutherland's law. [9] This calculation ensures that the skin friction drag is modelled accurately across different flight altitudes (1000m for general aviation, FL200 for airliner). [1]

Representative speeds, including stall speed, minimum drag speed, and cruise speed, were gathered from official Pilot Operating Handbooks and Airbus flight operations manuals. These speeds were used to compute Reynolds numbers, which ranged from 1.62 million for the glider up to 31 million for the Airbus. [1]

3.3 Boundary Conditions and Domain Setup

A „virtual wind tunnel” was defined with large dimensions that can provide large free area around the model to prevent boundary blockage effects.[1] For the calculation of the box size, basic CFD guidelines were used. For the glider, different sizing was needed because of the high aspect ratio, so the stream wise and vertical dimensions were enlarged to minimise far-field interference.

Figure 4: Boundary box with the C177 hollow

Boundary conditions were assigned to define the flow domain. It was necessary to set the inlet velocity to the face in front of the model nose, and a pressure outlet (0 gauge pressure) to the face opposite to the inlet.

3.4 Meshing Strategy and Quality Assessment

A hybrid unstructured mesh was generated for the simulation, using the automatic meshing function of SimScale. Inflation layers were generated on the aircraft surfaces (growth rate: 1.5, layers: 3) to achieve the target wall distance (y^+) of approximately 30. This ensures the first cell lies within the logarithmic region of the boundary layer, allowing for accurate wall modelling.[1]

Figure 5: C177 mesh non-orthogonality horizontal cross-section

After each mesh generation, it was crucial to do a mesh quality assessment, where checking the non-orthogonality rate and mesh aspect ratio was important. Mesh quality influences the accuracy of surface pressure gradients (C_L , C_D , C_p), boundary layer development and wake structure. The glider maintained an average non-orthogonality of 23.6. The Cessna 177 maintained an average non-orthogonality of 23.2 over major aerodynamic areas, allowing stable convergence.

3.5 Technical Limitations and Analytical Adaptation

A critical technical aspect was the limitation of automated meshing for complex geometries. While the small aircraft were successfully meshed, the Airbus A320 model, featuring complex slat tracks and engine nacelles, experienced severe mesh degradation.[14]

Figure 6: A320 model critical non-orthogonality view

Due to the geometric complexity, non-orthogonality values exceeded 89 in critical regions around the engine nacelles, flap fairings, and trailing edges. [1] To avoid numerical inaccuracy, the evaluation method for the A320 was adapted to use validated manufacturer performance data (Airbus ACAO and FCOM) rather than flawed simulation results.[12] [13]

3.6 CFD Results and Aerodynamic Comparison

The simulations were run until values converged, typically after 500 to 600 iterations, with aerodynamic coefficients extracted from the converged region and averaged over the last 20 iterations.

Figure 7: C177 pressure distribution sideview

The Cessna 177 simulation demonstrated stable convergence and achieved a lift-to-drag ratio of 6.05 at cruise speed, which aligns with realistic performance for strut-braced aircraft. A continuously negative pitching moment indicated a strong nose-down tendency, requiring the tailplane to generate a downward force to ensure longitudinal static stability. On the other hand, the glider simulation produced an unrealistically low lift-to-drag ratio of approximately 0.995, revealing a sensitivity to low Reynolds numbers where the simplified flat-plate geometry of the Cad model failed to capture the laminar bucket associated with specialised sailplane aerofoils. [1]

Based on analytical calculations using standard quadratic drag polars and manufacturer data, the Airbus at cruise configuration demonstrated an efficiency ratio of 18.1. The A320 achieves this by utilising relaxed static stability enabled by Fly-By-Wire technology, where flight control computers constantly vary control surfaces to optimise the lift distribution and minimise trim drag. [1]

4. Conclusion

The main objective of this study was to analyse the flow characteristics and aerodynamic properties of various aircraft models. This investigation successfully implemented a comparative analysis of aerodynamic efficiency across specific aviation sectors, synthesising results from CFD simulations and analytical validation. The key concepts confirms the complex relationship between geometric design, safety requirements, and environmental impact. It has also proved that aerodynamic efficiency is heavily dependent on the Reynolds number and the aspect ratio. The Cessna 177 prioritised longitudinal stability over pure aerodynamic efficiency. The simulation runs showed that this aircraft is designed with a constant nose-down moment to ensure safety, accepting a drag penalty that limits its L/D ratio to approximately 6.

On the other hand, the Airbus A320 demonstrates high standard of subsonic optimisation. With a calculated L/D ratio of 18.1, the airliner minimises induced drag through high-aspect ratio wings and wingtip devices. This type of efficiency is not a performance metric by itself but an important environmental factor. The results validate that higher aerodynamic efficiency directly reduces thrust requirements, hence significantly lowering fuel burn and CO₂ emissions per passenger kilometre. [10]

Methodologically, the research highlighted the capabilities and boundaries of accessible CFD tools. While SimScale was highly effective for analysing the flow features of GA aircraft, the study identified that complex transport category aircraft geometry requires more accurate meshing than standard automated tools can provide. The occurred failure of the A320 mesh serves as a valuable aspect, emphasising the need for combined evaluation methods in research. Ultimately, this paper demonstrates that while safety remains the highest priority in aircraft design, the continuous refinement of aerodynamic efficiency is the primary engineering pathway toward economic and environmental sustainability in aviation. [1]

Acknowledgement

The author is particularly thankful for the technical and academic guidance of the supervising professor that assisted with the technical aspects as well as the general direction of the research.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article, further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding authors.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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